

DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, SPECTRAL CHARACTERISATION AND ANTIBACTERIAL SCREENING OF SOME NOVEL 2-(2-ETHYLIMINO-4-SUBSTITUTEDIMINO-1,3,5-DITHIAZINE BEARING WITH PYRIMIDINE CORE

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ABSTRACT

In recent times in the laboratory, synthesis of 2-(2-Ethylimino-4-substitutedimino-1,3,5-dithiazino)aminopyrimidine (**IIIa-e**) were synthesized by refluxing 2-(5-ethyl-2,4-dithiobiureto) pyrimidine (**I**) with alkyl/arylisocyanodichlorides (**IIa-e**) in acetone-ethanol medium in 1:1 molar proportion. The structures of all the synthesized compounds were acceptable on the basis of chemical characteristics, elemental analysis, spectral studies and their antibacterial screening against the gram positive and gram negative bacteria such as *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *A. Aerogenes*, *B. Subtilis* and *B. Megatherium*.*etc.*

INTRODUCTION

Heterocycles containing organic molecules are more fascinating, because they are convenient in a variety of applications, a multitude of uses are included by the heterocycles' size and heteroatom diversity. These compound nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur are composed of six member¹⁻⁵, five member⁶⁻⁷ fused heterocycles with aromatic rings. Particularly noteworthy are the numerous biological and industrial uses for heterocycles that combine sulphur and nitrogen in one ring. Six member two sulphur and one nitrogen atom prepare 1,3,5-dithiazine. It is one of the six member heterocycles that functions as a strong medication in the sectors of medicine, agriculture, and industry⁹⁻⁸.

Tayade¹⁰, Pathe¹¹ and Mur¹² Synthesized numerous heterocycles containing 1,3,5-dithiazines as main nucleus. Each 1,3,5-dithiazino moiety has different applications according to the substituent attached to the basic nucleus of the 1,3,5-dithiazine. It has been also observed during literature study that, 1,3,5-dithiazino

nucleus and its derivatives possesses biological and medicinal effective properties¹³⁻¹⁴.

Substituted isocyanodichlorides were used by researchers to synthesise 1,3,5-dithiazines in the laboratory. This 1,3,5-dithiazine synthesis technique is quicker, less complicated, less expensive and requires less time.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

All the chemical used were of loba chemie (AR grade).

Method

In the present experiment for the synthesis of different substituted 1,3,5-dithiazino aminopyrimidine is conventional refluxing under electronic water bath for different hours for different experiment.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used for the synthesis were purified. After refluxing the purity of the compounds were checked by TLC (aluminium TLC) with thin layer thickness of 200 um. The melting points of all synthesise compounds will be recorded using hot paraffin bath. The carbon and hydrogen analysis were carried out on Carlo-Ebra-1106 analyser Nitrogen estimation were carried out with colmon-N-analyzer-29. IR spectra were recorded with Bruker spectrometer in the range 4000-400 cm⁻¹. PMR spectra were recorded on VARIAN 400 MHz spectrometer with TMS as internal standard using CDCL₃ and DMSO Solvent.

GENERAL PROCEDURE

A reaction of 2-(5-ethyl-2,4-dithiobiureto)pyrimidine (**I**) and substitutedisocyanodichloride (**IIa-e**) in 1:1 molar ratio refluxed on water bath in acetone-ethanol medium for 2 hours. The evolution of the hydrochloride gas was clearly observed during refluxion. After distillation of excess solvent orange product isolated which on basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide orange crystalline products obtained.

Similar, procedure was adopted for the synthesis of all the derivatives in the series.

The tentative reaction for the formation of product is depicted below,

Reaction

Similarly, 2-(5-ethyl-2,4-dithiobiureto)pyrimidine (**I**) were react with phenylisocyanochloride (**IIa**), ethylisocyanodichloride (**IIb**), tertbutylisocyanodichloride (**IIc**), p-tolyisocyanodichloride (**IId**) and 4-chlorophenylisocyanodichloride(**IIe**) by the above mentioned method to isolate 2-(2-ethylimino-4-phenylimino-1,3,5-dithiazino) aminopyrimidine (**IIIa**), 2-[2,4-di(ethylimino)-1,3,5-dithiazino] aminopyrimidine (**IIIb**), 2-(2-ethylimino-4-tertbutylimino-1,3,5-dithiazino) aminopyrimidine (**IIIc**), 2-[2-ethylimino-4-(4-methylphenylimino)-1,3,5-dithiazino] aminopyrimidine (**IIId**) and 2-[2-ethylimino-4-(4-chlorophenylimino)-1,3,5-dithiazino] aminopyrimidine (**IIIe**) respectively

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Spectral characterization results for all the synthesized compounds are given below

Spectral Characterization

1) 2-(2-ethylimino-4-phenylimino-1,3,5-dithiazino)aminopyrimidine (**IIIa**)

Colour-Yellow solid, **Molecular formula**- $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$, **Yield** 86%, **M.P.** 134°C , **% Composition found (calculated)** C-52.50 , H-4.83 , N-25.20, S-23.21 , **FTIR (Kbr) vcm**- 3226.22 N-H stretching, 3009.47 (C-H Ar Stretching), 3140.38 (N-H Amido), 1948.37 (C-H Ar Bending.), 1170.99 (C=S Stretching), 760.04(=C-H bending); **¹H NMR (400MHz CDCl₃ δ ppm)**, 8.4 ppm (2H, double, CH), 7.3ppm (2H, CH, doublet), 7.4 ppm (2H, , doublet CH), 3.3 ppm (1H, singlet NH), 4.5 ppm 1H singlet, 7.49 1H triplet CH benzene, **Mass m/z** 342.50

2) 2-(2-ethylimino-4-ethylimino-1,3,5-dithiazino)aminopyrimidine (IIIb)

Colour-Yellow solid, **Molecular formula**- $C_{11}H_{14}N_6S_2$, **Yield** 81%, **M.P.** 139⁰C, %
Composition found (calculated) C-44.90 , H-4.83 , N-24.20, S-20.21 , **FTIR (Kbr)**
vcm- 3212.22 N-H stretching, 3021.47 (C-H Ar Stretching), 3165.38 (N-H Amido),
1947.37 (C-H Ar Bending,), 1180.99 (C=S Stretching), 730.04(=C-H bending); **1H**
NMR (400MHz CDCL₃ δ ppm), 8.2 ppm (2H, double, CH), 7.2ppm (2H, CH,
doublet), 7.3 ppm (2H, , doublet CH), 3.3 ppm (1H, singlet NH), 4.4 ppm 1H singlet,
2.2 ppm 2H quartet, 2.3 ppm 3H triplet **Mass m/z** 294.20

3) 2-(2-ethylimino-4-tert-butylimino-1,3,5-dithiazino)aminopyrimidine (IIIc)

Colour-Yellow solid, **Molecular formula**- $C_{13}H_{18}N_6S_2$, **Yield** 78%, **M.P.** 156⁰C, %
Composition found (calculated) C-53.90 , H-3.83 , N-24.20, S-18.21 , **FTIR (Kbr)**
vcm- 3223.22 N-H stretching, 3001.47 (C-H Ar Stretching), 3136.38 (N-H Amido),
1946.37 (C-H Ar Bending,), 1174.99 (C=S Stretching), 685.04(=C-H bending); **1H**
NMR (400MHz CDCL₃ δ ppm), 8.0 ppm (2H, double, CH), 7.2ppm (2H, CH,
doublet), 7.1 ppm (2H, , doublet CH), 3.4 ppm (1H, singlet NH), 4.6 ppm 1H singlet,
2.1 ppm 2H quartet, 2.4 ppm 3H triplet, 2.4 9H singlet **Mass m/z** 322.10

4) 2-[2-ethylimino-4-(4-methylphenylimino)-1,3,5-dithiazino]aminopyrimidine (IIIId)

Colour-Yellow solid, **Molecular formula**- $C_{16}H_{16}N_6S_2$, **Yield** 83%, **M.P.** 175⁰C, %
Composition found (calculated) C-53.90 , H-4.83 , N-25.20, S-23.21 , **FTIR (Kbr)**
vcm- 3245.22 N-H stretching, 3021.47 (C-H Ar Stretching), 3146.38 (N-H Amido),
1966.37 (C-H Ar Bending,), 1186.99 (C=S Stretching), 880.04(=C-H bending); **1H**
NMR (400MHz CDCL₃ δ ppm), 8.4 ppm (2H, double, CH), 7.1ppm (2H, CH,
doublet), 7.2 ppm (2H, , doublet CH), 3.4 ppm (1H, singlet NH), 4.6 ppm 1H singlet,
7.39 1H triplet CH benzene, 2.3 ppm 2H quartet, 2.4 ppm 3H triplet **Mass m/z**
356.05

5) 2-[2-ethylimino-4-(4-chlorophenylimino)-1,3,5-dithiazino]aminopyrimidine (IIIIf)

Colour-Yellow solid, **Molecular formula**- $C_{15}H_{13}N_6S_2$, **Yield** 79%, **M.P.**126⁰C, %
Composition found (calculated) C-47.90 , H-4.83 , N-18.20, S-09.21 , **FTIR (Kbr)**

vcm- 324122 N-H stretching, 3023.47 (C-H Ar Stretching), 3236.38 (N-H Amido), 1846.37 (C-H Ar Bending), 1174.99 (C=S Stretching), 690.04(=C-H bending); **¹H NMR (400MHz CDCL₃ δ ppm)**, 8.5 ppm (2H, double, CH), 7.1ppm (2H, CH, doublet), 7.2 ppm (2H, , doublet CH), 3.4 ppm (1H, singlet NH), 4.6 ppm 1H singlet, 7.39 1H triplet CH benzene, **Mass** m/z 376.10.

CONCLUSION

In the present work is cheaper and less time consuming method for synthesis of organic compound (IIIa-e). In all the synthesized compounds give the maximum yield of product (III a-e). A variety of pyrimidine based 1,3,5-dithiazine derivative can be synthesized for their antimicrobial activities adopting the method.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES

Antimicrobial activity

All the synthesized compounds (**III-a**) to (**III-e**) were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. typhi*, *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *A. Aerogenes*, *B. Subtilis* and *B. Megatherium*. by disc diffusion method was performed using mueller hinton agar as well as nutrient agar medium. Each and every compound was tested at conc. 50 µg/ml in ethanol. The zone of inhibition of all the synthesized compounds were measured after 24 hour incubation at 37 °C. Standard drug used for comparison the activity was Ciprofloxacin.

Table No. 1.1 - Antibacterial activity of synthesized compound against bacteria (Zone of inhibition in mm) (after 24 hrs at 37 °C temp)							
SR No	Compd.	Gram positive			Gram negative		
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. megatherium</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. aerogenes</i>
1	SBS-IIIa	17	14	12	14	16	11
2	SBS-IIIb	11	12	14	14	11	12
3	SBS-IIIc	11	11	12	11	11	11
4	SBS-IIId	10	12	12	12	11	11
5	SBS-IIIE	16	12	14	12	14	12
6	Std Ciprofloxacin	18	16	20	18	20	14

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